

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
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Sacramento, CA 95814

In Reply Refer To:
08FBDT00-2020-F-0038

September 30, 2020

Ms. Sahrye Cohen
North Branch Chief, Regulatory Division
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
450 Golden Gate Ave., 4th floor
San Francisco, CA 94102

Subject: Formal Section 7 Consultation on the Lower Walnut Creek Restoration Project,
Contra Costa County, California (Corps File No: 2019-00431S)

Dear Ms. Cohen:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (Corps), November 19, 2019, request for formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Lower Walnut Creek Restoration Project (Project), Contra Costa County, California. At issue are the proposed Project's effects on the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*; SMHM), California clapper rail¹ (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*; CCR), soft bird's-beak (*Chloropyron molle* ssp. *molle*; SBB), the federally threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*; DS), and delta smelt critical habitat. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit, pursuant to section 404 of the Clean Water Act, for the Contra Costa County Flood Control and Water Conservation District's (District, applicant) plan to restore coastal wetlands near the southern shore of Suisun Bay to increase habitat quality, diversity and connectivity. The Project is located along the Contra Costa County shoreline, northeast of the City of Martinez, California, specifically from the mouth of Walnut Creek at Suisun Bay upstream along Walnut Creek and Pacheco Creek for approximately four cumulative miles. Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12(j), the Corps submitted a biological assessment for our review. Your findings conclude that the

¹ Regarding taxonomic assignment and nomenclature for the California clapper rail, until such time as the Service officially adopts changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union (from California clapper rail [*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*] to Ridgway's Rail [*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*]), the Service maintains the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) as used in this current correspondence.

proposed Project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect SMHM and CCR and that it may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect SBB, DS and critical habitat for DS.

This document analyzes effects to federally listed species and critical habitat of the first and second phases of this three-phase restoration project only, as well as monitoring, maintenance, and adaptive management of the project. The third phase of the restoration project, the public access component, will be led by the John Muir Land Trust (JMLT) and therefore could involve future consultation with the Corps associated with a separate permit application. Effects of the construction and use of public access facilities is not covered in this biological opinion, but will be subject to a separate consultation with the Corps if these activities may affect federally listed species and/or critical habitat.

The Bay Restoration Regulatory Integration Team (BRRIT) was formed in August 2019 to improve the permitting process for multi-benefit habitat restoration projects and associated flood management and public access infrastructure in the San Francisco Bay and along the shoreline of the nine Bay Area counties, excluding the Delta Primary Zone. The BRRIT reviews and permits projects selected, or eligible for, funding through Measure AA, a local parcel tax measure passed in 2016. Since Project development began years before BRRIT formation, the Project did not receive the benefit of BRRIT pre-application coordination, however it did receive funding through Measure AA and is slated to be one of the first projects permitted by the BRRIT.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: 1) the Corps' letter requesting formal consultation; 2) the revised Lower Walnut Creek Restoration Project Biological Assessment, dated October 2019, for the proposed Project; 3) the Corps' revised determination (for CCR) and request for formal consultation; 4) several revised project descriptions and effects analyses; 5) the Monitoring and Adaptive Management Plan (MAMP), dated July 2020; 6) multiple in person, telephone and video meetings with the Corps and District; 7) multiple emails clarifying project details; and 8) other information available to the Service.

Soft Bird's-Beak

The applicant proposes to do grading, excavating, and other major earthmoving consistent with tidal marsh restoration projects. However, rare plant surveys conducted in 2019 and 2020, in accordance with the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) *Guidelines for Assessing the Effects of Proposed Projects on Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Plants and Natural Communities* (CDFW 2018) and covering all Project site suitable habitat, did not result in observations of the species. If the species is later observed on the project site, locations will be flagged and avoided with a 40-foot buffer around each individual, within which no construction work would occur. A Service-approved biologist will oversee installation of a temporary mesh fence at least 4 feet tall marking the 40-foot buffer. The buffer zone established by the fencing will be marked by a sign stating: "This is habitat of soft bird's-beak, a federally listed endangered plant species and must not be disturbed. This species is protected by [the ESA of 1973, as amended/CESA/California Native Plant Protection Act]". Though unlikely to be identified on the Project site, any SBB individuals will be completely avoided by construction, therefore the proposed Project is not likely to adversely affect SBB.

Delta Smelt

The proposed Project occurs near the Carquinez Bridge which historically has high salinity in the late summer/early fall, which makes the area less suitable for the DS when construction will occur. Delta smelt will likely be further upstream towards the confluence of the Sacramento and San Joaquin Rivers nearer to the low salinity zone.

The proposed Project includes in-channel work such as breaching of levees. Levee lowering will include a phased removal of earth to provide continuous flood protection while setback levees are constructed and to limit the risk of uncontrolled breaching. The construction contractor will be required to phase levee removal to prevent site inundation. Breaches will be completed by long reach excavators working from the lowered levee on either one or both sides of the breach to be excavated, with excavated material loaded into low ground pressure track dump trucks and hauled for fill placement elsewhere.

While work will be conducted at a low tide, and utilizing a silt curtain, construction activities may result in the short-term, temporary disturbance and resuspension of benthic sediments. Increased turbidity levels associated with in-water construction activities will be minor, relatively short-lived, and generally localized to the immediate area of construction. Following construction, sediments will disperse and background levels will be restored within hours of disturbance. In addition, normal circulation and strong currents within Lower Walnut Creek will rapidly circulate and disperse water temporarily affected by construction activities. Turbidity plumes will disperse within a matter of hours, and the particulate concentrations will be diluted to levels that will pose a less-than-significant threat to water quality or aquatic wildlife.

The applicant proposes a work window from September 1 through November 30 for in-channel activities, which is consistent with the Service's recommended work window for DS and to conduct shoreline activities during low tide. The applicant also proposes to conduct the following measure:

- Prior to the start of construction of the tidal connector channels, the District shall isolate the work area from Lower Walnut and Pacheco Creeks using a silt curtain with a floating boom installed at the confluence of the new tidal channels and the creeks. Installation of the silt curtain shall contain turbidity and sediment resulting from construction activity, exclude fish from access to the active construction area, and allow water to pass between the connector channels and the creeks with the tides. The curtain shall span the width of the connector channel and shall be at least 6 feet tall to maintain a fish barrier at high tide. The curtain will consist of permeable filter fabric supported by a line of floats on the water surface and a line of weights on the channel bottom. The curtain shall be monitored and maintained regularly.

Delta Smelt Critical Habitat

Critical habitat for the DS occurs along the shoreline of the project area and may provide some or all of the primary constituent elements (PCE) identified in the listing of the designated critical habitat. PCE #1 is physical habitat for spawning. Spawning occurs primarily in the sloughs and

shallow edge areas in the Delta and the Napa River. Captive breeding has indicated sandy or gravel areas are preferred (Bennett 2005). The Action Area encompasses critical habitat that may be suitable for spawning. Spawning activity occurred historically around the project area during “wet” years of significant freshwater outflow into San Pablo Bay (CDFW 2019). The proposed action is not expected to remove available spawning habitat substrate that may be present offshore. It is not known what substrates exist in shallow areas near proposed levee breaches at Suisun Bay and Walnut Creek. However, even if sandy or gravel areas appropriate for spawning exist, the permanent change in the physical structure of this shallow water habitat will be restricted to no more than 10 levee breaches (approximately 0.12 acre) while the restoration of the area as a whole is likely to open up large areas newly available as spawning habitat to DS. Therefore, shallow water habitat removed at the levee breach locations is expected to be insignificant in terms of loss of spawning habitat substrate. PCE #2 is suitable water quality for all life stages. The proposed Project does not discharge effluent or reduce the dilution properties of the available water through diversion, however there could be a temporary effect to localized water quality. PCE #3 relates to river flow. The proposed Project is not expected to alter river flows of the Sacramento River or the San Joaquin River. PCE #4 is salinity for rearing. The proposed Project is not expected to have any effect on salinity, since the river flows will not be affected, thus not affecting the position of the low salinity zone.

PCEs #1 and 2 may be temporarily affected during breaching activities, however they will remain intact and, over time, a net improvement in the conditions related to these PCEs is expected. Implementation of the project will create approximately 102 acres of tidal wetland and tidal channel habitat, which, in addition to providing fish with increased access to these delta-limited habitats, should increase aquatic productivity and export to the surrounding areas. As breaches along the Suisun Bay and Walnut Creek shorelines are expected to be relatively small and, along with lowering of levees, contribute to the development of considerable new acreage of potentially suitable spawning and rearing habitat, effects of the removal of critical habitat elements are considered insignificant or discountable.

Based on the analyses above, the Service concurs that the proposed Project is not likely to adversely affect the SBB, DS, or DS critical habitat. The Corps has determined, that due to lack of recent protocol surveys and the applicant’s decision to assume presence of SMHM and CCR in the Action Area, that the proposed Project may affect and is likely to adversely affect SMHM and CCR. The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed Project on the SMHM and CCR.

CONSULTATION HISTORY

February 8, 2017	The Service attended an initial kickoff meeting to discuss the preliminary Project, prior to formation of BRRIT.
July 24, 2018	The Service participated in a conference call regarding the interim vegetation management for the Project.
August 9, 2018	The District presented the preliminary Project at the Corps’ monthly pre-application meeting.

August 27, 2018	The Service participated in a conference call with the District and consultants.
September 18, 2019	As part of the BRRIT, the Service attended an informational meeting at the District's office immediately followed by a visit to the Project site.
November 22, 2019	The Service requested additional information from the applicant related to their biological assessment.
November 25, 2019	The Service received the Corps' November 19, 2019 letter requesting formal consultation for the proposed Project. The letter stated the Corps' determination that the proposed Project is likely to adversely affect SMHM but is not likely to adversely affect CCR, SBB, DS and critical habitat for DS.
November 26, 2019	The Service received the Corps' email revising the determination made regarding CCR in their formal request for consultation on SMHM. The Corps stated that given review of additional information, they now determined that the proposed Project is likely to adversely affect SMHM and CCR and not likely to adversely affect SBB, DS and critical habitat for DS.
December 10, 2019	The Service received the initial MAMP from the applicant.
January 14, 2020	The Service received the revised SMHM and CCR avoidance and minimization measures from the applicant.
January 17, 2020	The BRRIT submitted consolidated comments to the applicant on their MAMP.
January 21, 2020	The Service received revised SMHM avoidance and minimization measures from the applicant.
January 29, 2020	The Service attended a meeting with the applicant to discuss project changes between 65 and 95% design and received an updated table of acreage impacts per sub-habitat (95% design plan). After the meeting, the Service provided to the applicant a list of avoidance and minimization measures for SMHM and CCR agreed upon with the applicant at the meeting.
January 30, 2020	The Service received a revised project description for Phases 1 and 2 from the applicant.
January 31, 2020	The BRRIT provided to the applicant a list of highest priority MAMP issues (those that must be addressed before permits are issued).

February 12, 2020 The Service received revised SMHM and CCR avoidance and minimization measures from the applicant.

March 11, 2020 The Service attended a meeting to discuss SMHM avoidance and minimization measures, including fencing strategy.

March 17, 2020 The Service attended a meeting to discuss permitting pathways and permitting challenges involving realignment of the Bureau of Reclamation's Shortcut Pipeline.

May 4, 2020 The Service provided a reminder to the applicant about information still needed to begin consultation, including information on adaptive management and maintenance activities.

May 12, 2020 The Service received the 2020 CCR survey report from the applicant.

June 3, 2020 The Service received supplemental information from the applicant relating to the highest priority MAMP concerns of the BRRIT.

June 17, 2020 The BRRIT provided consolidated comments on the revised MAMP to the applicant.

June 18, 2020 The applicant requested CCR avoidance and minimization measure exceptions and the Service received the applicant's revised project description for Phases 1 and 2.

June 19, 2020 The Service received the revised table of acreage impacts per habitat type (Phase 1, 95% design; Phase 2, 30% design) from the applicant.

June 26, 2020 The Service provided a reminder to the applicant that they must submit an effects analysis for the adaptive management and maintenance activities added to the project description before formal consultation can begin.

July 1, 2020 The Corps informed the BRRIT that the applicant has decided to remove the Shortcut Pipeline realignment element from the project description.

July 6, 2020 The Service received the revised MAMP from the applicant.

July 9, 2020 The Service received the 2019 Rare Plant Survey Report from the applicant.

July 13, 2020 The Service received revised sections 5.3 and 5.4 of Chapter 5 (Effects Analysis) of the biological assessment (revised to incorporate discussion of effects to species from maintenance and adaptive management actions added to MAMP).

- July 20, 2020 The Service emailed the Corps and the applicant articulating the need for resolution on a CCR minimization measure before initiation of formal consultation can begin.
- July 29, 2020 The Service received the 2020 Rare Plant Survey Report from the applicant.
- July 30, 2020 The Service received clarification, during a conference call, of a minimization measure relating to construction activities within 300 feet of a breeding CCR detection.
- August 21, 2020 The Service received another revised project description with figures, forwarded from the applicant by the Corps, reflecting removal of the Shortcut Pipeline component and associated revised acreages. The Service subsequently confirmed to the Corps that all information required for formal consultation has been received.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed Project will restore and enhance coastal wetlands and adjacent habitats along the southern shoreline of Suisun Bay and from the mouth of Walnut Creek at Suisun Bay upstream along Walnut Creek and Pacheco Creek, improving habitat quality, diversity, and connectivity along four cumulative miles of creek channel, over approximately 384 acres in total.

Scheduling/Phasing

The proposed Project is slated to occur in two phases. The first phase entails construction beginning in spring 2021 in the North and South Reaches, as well as vegetation management within the Pacheco Reach. The second phase entails construction during fall 2021 in the Middle Reach.

As stated above, the third phase comprises the public access component for the entire project, including construction of access trails and amenities such as an interpretive center. This phase is not considered part of the proposed Project for purposes of this consultation, but may be the subject of a future consultation if it may affect federally listed species and/or critical habitat.

The proposed Project will restore and enhance approximately 126 acres of tidal wetland, 15 acres of non-tidal wetland, 14 acres of tidal waters, 3 acres of non-tidal waters, and 119 acres of transitional and upland areas (lowland and upland grasslands and scrub). See Table 1 for the breakdown of proposed restored habitat acreage by reach. A key feature of the proposed Project is adjacent transitional lowlands which have been designed to be successional habitats, gradually converting to tidal marsh with sea level rise.

TABLE 1. Restored Habitat Acreage by Reach

Habitat Type	North Reach (acres)		Middle Reach (acres)		South Reach (acres)		Pacheco Creek Reach (acres)		Total (acres)	
	Restored	Enhanced	Restored	Enhanced	Restored	Enhanced	Restored	Enhanced	Restored	Enhanced
Upland										
Upland	46.16	0.02	9.17	0.02	10.07	0.00	7.85	0.00	73.25	0.04
Lowland Grassland	24.06	0.00	6.42	0.00	1.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.46	0.00
Developed (trail/road/parking)	4.01	0.00	3.49	0.00	2.02	0.00	3.87	0.00	13.40	0.00
Non-Tidal Wetlands										
Pickleweed Marsh	10.99	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.00	7.08	0.72	0.00	11.99	7.08
Seasonal Wetland	2.73	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.13	0.00	2.94	0.10
Tidal Wetlands										
Brackish Tidal Marsh	29.34	72.43	7.55	21.83	9.52	4.84	12.34	0.00	58.74	99.10
Pickleweed Marsh (Tidal)	31.89	0.00	29.51	0.00	5.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	66.91	0.00
Non-Tidal Waters										
Scald/Playa	2.03	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.75	0.00	0.00	2.06	0.78
Seasonal Pond	0.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.00	0.72	0.35
Tidal Waters										
Tidal Channels	7.32	0.00	1.92	0.20	1.84	0.14	2.45	0.00	13.54	0.34
<i>Subtotal</i>	<i>159.25</i>	<i>72.49</i>	<i>58.44</i>	<i>22.05</i>	<i>30.96</i>	<i>13.27</i>	<i>27.37</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>276.02</i>	<i>107.81</i>
Total	231.74		80.49		44.23		27.37		383.82	

Key project elements in both phases will generally include:

- sensitive species surveys,
- site preparation (including invasive plant removal, clearing and grubbing of vegetation, fencing, and construction of temporary access roads),
- excavation and grading of new tidal channels,
- placement of silt curtains,
- construction of setback levees in the South and Middle reaches to provide flood protection,
- creation of ecotonal areas with excavated materials,
- breaches and phased lowering of existing levees, and
- revegetation of terrestrial lowland and upland habitat.

North Reach

The North Reach includes tidal and seasonal wetland restoration within four quadrants. The design will preserve large portions of the site at supratidal elevations (above the elevations of present day tidal marsh) with the expectation that these areas will gradually convert to tidal marsh habitats over time as sea levels rise. The proposed Project will create a mosaic of lowland terrestrial habitats in the areas adjacent to the tidal marsh restoration. These habitats will include a mix of grasslands, seasonal wetlands, and sandy alkali playa flat. Restored tidal marsh areas will be fully tidal east of the Contra Costa County Sanitary District outfall pipeline and muted tidal west of the outfall pipeline.

Approximately 108 acres of fringing tidal marsh habitat within the overall project area boundary, but outside of the North Reach work limit, will be indirectly enhanced by the proposed Project through increasing tidal and habitat connectivity within the existing fringing tidal marsh.

Middle Reach

Tidal marsh will be restored by breaching and lowering the existing flood protection levees along Walnut Creek and Pacheco Creek to restore tidal inundation to the existing non-tidal wetlands. New tidal channels will be excavated within the restored wetlands and adjacent existing fringe marsh, to connect the restored wetlands to the creek. The existing levees will be lowered to create predominantly high marsh habitat, but may also include marsh ponds and small areas of terrestrial lowland grasslands and uplands. Based on the sediment supply from the creek and estuary, mudflat areas in the Middle Reach are expected to accrete to tidal marsh elevations within 5-10 years of construction.

The existing private landfill perimeter access road will be improved to support landfill operations and access for District maintenance. New drainage swales will be constructed on the upslope side of the improved perimeter access route to direct stormwater runoff from the landfill into existing non-tidal basins to the north and south of the Middle Reach project area. Two new short sections of levee will be constructed at the upstream and downstream ends of the reach and will connect to the existing levees along Pacheco and Lower Walnut Creeks.

South Reach

The South Reach will be restored by breaching and lowering the existing flood protection levees along Walnut and Pacheco Creeks to restore tidal inundation to the existing non-tidal wetlands. New tidal channels will be excavated within the restored wetlands and adjacent existing fringe marsh, to connect the restored wetlands to the creeks. The existing levees will be lowered to create predominantly high and mid marsh habitat, but will also include areas of terrestrial lowland grasslands and uplands. Flood protection will be provided by two new setback levees along the western boundary of the South Reach, forming a horseshoe shaped levee alignment. This alignment avoids potential settlement issues affecting a buried water supply pipeline (Shortcut Pipeline), owned by Bureau of Reclamation and managed by Contra Costa Water District (CCWD) and an inactive recycled water pipeline owned by CCWD. The project site will be designed to facilitate the implementation of future public access improvements, including the extension of the Iron Horse Trail along the new setback levee, construction of a pedestrian crossing over the Burlington Northern Santa Fe railroad, and a pedestrian bridge over Pacheco Creek, which will be included in a future Corps permit application (not addressed in this biological opinion).

Pacheco Reach

Invasive species removal and native vegetation planting will occur along the Pacheco Creek reach of the project site. Vegetation management activities could include removal of invasive species using hand, low impact mechanical, and/or herbicide application methods.

Equipment

Equipment anticipated for construction includes: mowers, long and short reach excavators, bulldozers/graders, rotary ditchers, wheel dump trucks, low ground pressure track dump trucks, track pulled scrapers, conventional big wheel scrapers, water trucks, pumps, rollers, sheepsfoot compactors, cranes and concrete mixers.

Revegetation

Revegetation will be accomplished using a combination of hydroseeding, drill seeding, plug planting, and transplanting of dormant sod fragments and/or discing of sod fragments into the finished grades. Revegetation will occur in all three reaches, in addition to Pacheco Creek.

Monitoring, Maintenance and Adaptive Management

In addition to the construction itself, the proposed Project entails monitoring, ongoing maintenance and adaptive management elements to occur for a period of 10 years after construction. The MAMP, which has been preliminarily reviewed by the resource agencies, will be finalized and provided to the Service prior to commencement of construction. The MAMP describes monitoring actions that will be conducted to evaluate project progress toward desired outcomes. The final MAMP will be consistent with the current state of the framework being developed by the Wetlands Regional Monitoring Program and includes monitoring metrics and performance criteria for hydrology, geomorphology, vegetation, and wetlands development. Further details in regards to these elements are described in the MAMP and are described briefly

below.

Proposed Project Monitoring

- **Hydrology** (As-built plus Years 1, 2, 3, 5, 7 and 10) - Water levels will be monitored to detect tidal range.
- **Water Quality** (Years 1, 3 and 5) – Temperature, dissolved oxygen and electrical conductivity will be monitored.
- **Geomorphology** (Pre-construction, as-built, plus Years 1, 2, 3, 5, 7 and 10) - Channel development and tidal circulation patterns will be monitored in planform and cross-section. The District will continue to observe geomorphic changes along Walnut Creek in order to monitor the flood conveyance capacity of the creek channel.
- **Vegetation** (Years 1, 2, 3, 5, 7 and 10) - Photo-documentation, primarily remote sensing via airplane, with sufficient ground-truthing will be implemented to determine vegetation establishment. Parameters monitored will be percent cover, rate of natural colonization, vegetation health, and species diversity. Concurrent weed surveys will be conducted.
 - If vegetation cover (detailed in the MAMP) is within the lower half of the proposed range of success criteria during monitoring Years 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, and 10, the District will consult with the agencies to determine whether adaptive management is needed. Consultation will include phone or email notification to the Service and if necessary, one meeting to discuss vegetation results and recommendations. Regardless of whether the Project has met performance criteria for Years 1-5, the Project will meet with the BRRIT to discuss vegetation monitoring data collected through Year 5, to evaluate site conditions, and adjust vegetation success criteria as needed.
- **SMHM** trapping (Pre-construction and Year 5, plus Years 7 and 10 if necessary) – Pre- and post-construction monitoring will be conducted to determine if Project habitat restoration goals and objectives are being met. The MAMP details specific required occupancy thresholds and was determined in coordination with CDFW and the Service.
- **Wetlands** (Pre-construction and Year 5 for wetland condition, Year 10 for wetland extent) - Re-delineate jurisdictional wetlands to verify that the target wetland acreage has been attained.

Pre-construction monitoring will be used to establish pre-Project (existing) conditions for vegetation and channel planform. After construction, the monitoring data above will be collected periodically, for a period of 10 years post-construction, to assess restoration success and will be detailed in annual monitoring reports. Data will be used to inform any potential remedial or adaptive management action.

Maintenance

While the proposed Project was designed to require only minimal active operation, the District will perform routine observation and maintenance of the flood protection infrastructure, including the new

setback levees (Table 2) for a period of 10 after construction. Monitoring of levees will be conducted annually after construction and after major storm events. Regular inspection will occur, typically for erosion or rodent damage along the levee tops and slopes, to determine maintenance needs. Other maintenance may include: exploratory borings from top of levee road; removal, replacement, and compaction of material on top of levee road using small excavators, compactors; filling and compacting of rodent burrows and installation of appropriate stormwater best management practices, including wattles, coir rolls, or hydroseeding. In addition to repairs, typical ongoing, or routine, maintenance of the project site will consist of trash collection, security, trail inspection, vandalism damage repair, homeless encampment clean-up, fencing repair and cross culvert cleaning to ensure proper long term functioning of all parts of the proposed Project. Vegetation maintenance will be focused on routine mowing for fire suppression but may also be conducted to restrict the spread of target invasive exotic species by mechanical treatment (mowing, manual pull, mechanical scrape) and/or herbicide application, as determined by a qualified biologist/botanist, in response to particular site conditions. Other vegetation work may include propagation, replanting and augmentation of appropriate native species, led by the District, its partners, or volunteers.

Maintenance will be conducted using the same construction techniques, equipment and conservation measures used during initial construction of the proposed Project.

Adaptive Management

Should monitoring indicate that the proposed Project is not performing as intended, adaptive management activities will be triggered (Table 3) throughout and up to the 10 years after construction. If at Year 10 goals have not been met, the District will meet with the resource agencies to determine the reason for non-attainment and if further adaptive management is required, the monitoring period may be extended beyond Year 10. Unexpected trends in the biological or morphological characteristics of the site will require examination to determine if they are compromising the goals and objectives of the restoration Project or may cause undesired effects. If the proposed Project reaches a management trigger, possible adaptive management actions include excavation of debris or sediment, regrading of breaches or channels, placement of additional sediment control structures, increased invasive species control frequency, and replacement of native plantings.

Adaptive management will be conducted using the same construction techniques, equipment and conservation measures used during initial construction of the proposed Project.

**TABLE 2
SUMMARY OF ROUTINE MAINTENANCE OBJECTIVES, MONITORING, TRIGGERS, ACTIONS, AND LIMITS**

Objective	Monitoring Parameter	Maintenance Trigger	As Needed Applied Studies	Potential Maintenance Action¹	Maximum Limits
Maintain appropriate levels of flood protection along Lower Walnut and Pacheco creeks, as warranted by the land use.	Proper functioning and condition of levee, culvert, flapgate and headwall.	Cracking along the crown, settlement or sloughing of the levee top or side slopes, rodent burrows that may cause seepage pathways. Erosion or wasting of the levee slope, boils or other evidence of through or under seepage. Encroachments or unauthorized excavation into the levee prism that could compromise the levee's integrity. Levee foundation consolidation is greater than expected and reduces level of protection Interior drainage culvert / headwalls / flapgate no longer functioning as designed.	Evaluate conditions contributing to levee degradation. Evaluations may include topographic surveys, or geotechnical analyses.	Install erosion control measures along the levee toe. Repair boils or seepage issue. Remove encroachments, and restore levee or other damaged areas. Raise levee crown to restore design level of protection (i.e., original constructed elevation). Remove debris, replace culvert./ headwall / flapgate to restore functionality. (Note, culvert is not on stream or tidal channel, only provides interior drainage under levee.)	No more than 10 discrete locations (up to 100 linear feet each) of coir rolls, fabric placement, or minor regrading (not to exceed 5,000 sq ft) No more than 5 locations (up to 500 linear feet in length) and maximum input of 10,000 cubic yards of imported soil. No more than 10% of the total levee length would be repaired in any given year. Temporary disturbance not to exceed 5,000 sq ft in the vicinity of the culvert / headwall / flapgate being serviced. Minor debris removal (by hand) may occur annually. Anticipated timing of larger disturbance not to exceed once every 5 years.
	Proper functioning and condition of access road	Levee surface rutted and/or causing standing water on top of levee. Levee surface worn and muddy in inclement weather.	Visual inspection of road conditions	Regrade or renew gravel surface on top of levee	Regrade or renew gravel surface on top of levee no more than once every 5 years
Restore wetlands to improve ecological function and habitat quantity, quality, and connectivity (including upland transition zones) in the Lower Walnut Creek area for native, resident plant and animal species including special status species.	Proper functioning of restored lands	Presence of litter, vandalism damage, homeless encampments, fencing damage, or other trespassing.	Not Applicable	Trash collection, vandalism damage repair (including replacing vegetation), homeless encampment clean-up, fencing repair, install additional security measures (gates, bollards, etc. consistent with original design), general site cleanup. Modifications not consistent with original design would be discussed with BCDC)	Not Applicable.

NOTES:
¹ All applicable permit conditions and avoidance and minimization measures identified in the permits would be applied to Routine Maintenance Activities. If working within the permitted work windows is not feasible, then the District would notify and discuss with the agencies prior to conducting the activities to ensure that impacts are being minimized.

TABLE 3
SUMMARY OF ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT OBJECTIVES, MONITORING, TRIGGERS, ACTIONS, AND LIMITS

Objective	Monitoring Parameter	Management Trigger	Time Scale for Decision-Making	As Needed Applied Studies	Potential Management Action¹	Maximum Limits
Restore wetlands to improve ecological function and habitat quantity, quality, and connectivity (including upland transition zones) in the Lower Walnut Creek area for native, resident plant and animal species including special status species.	Water Levels	The site does not appear to be on the trajectory to be fully tidal after 10 years and causing reduced ecological function or habitat quality	Years 2-10	Determine (field observations, examine other success criteria, etc.) if tidal dampening is providing reduced ecological function or habitat quality; perform formal surveys or studies only if required.	Potential management actions may include excavation of sediment or debris from tidal channels.	Not to exceed clearing of 1 channel per year. Not to exceed 5,000 cubic yards in any given year, not to occur more than twice in 10 years. Not to exceed 1,000 linear feet., per event.
	Channel Development	The breach or channel configuration is not properly sized and is limiting planned tidal exchange or is failing to provide the expected ecological functions.	Years 1-10	Study if channel development is reducing ecological function.	Continue to monitor channel development. Excavate and/or regrade breaches or channels.	Not to exceed clearing of 1 channel per year. Not to exceed 5,000 cubic yards in any given year, not to occur more than twice in 10 years. Not to exceed 1,000 linear feet per event.
	Vegetation Establishment	Not meeting success criteria because rates of vegetation establishment are slower than predicted and/or plants are not appropriate for the ecotone.	Years 2-10	Study the causes of slow vegetation establishment. Have qualified personnel and agencies review the findings and assess whether observed trajectories require intervention.	Replanting of specified plant species, or if unanticipated conditions in ecotone indicate changes to plant palette is warranted.	50% replanting of original planting amount, exact location of the plantings may vary based on site conditions A new planting palette would not exceed 25% of the original planting plan in quantity or extent Native revegetation in areas not originally planted to help meet ecological goals

Objective	Monitoring Parameter	Management Trigger	Time Scale for Decision-Making	As Needed Applied Studies	Potential Management Action ¹	Maximum Limits
	Invasive Plants	Not meeting success criteria – unable to control target weeds	Years 0-10	If target weed species cannot be properly controlled, study the biotic response to specific invasive species that are particularly detrimental to the site.	Potential management actions may include increasing non-native invasive species control frequency or methods.	Increase treatment frequency up to 4 treatments per year (over the currently anticipated 2 treatments per year).
	Wetland Extent	If target wetland acreage is not obtained	Year 10	Investigate sources of sedimentation	Debris or sediment removal in channels to ensure full tidal exchange	Not to exceed clearing more than 1 channel of 500 linear feet per year.
		Sediment from upland areas is deposited over and smothers wetlands, reducing habitat quality	Years 1 - 10		Implement sediment control measures	Install additional sediment control measures (coir rolls, silt fence, etc.) at no more than 10 discrete upland locations to prevent deleterious sediment delivery.
Allow for future public access, education, and recreational opportunities.	Successful opening of the site to the public via public access partner, JMLT	Not applicable (JMLT)	TBD	Not applicable (JMLT)	Not applicable (JMLT)	Not applicable (JMLT)
Create sustainable benefits that consider future environmental changes such as sea level rise and sedimentation.	Distribution and evolution of habitats over the site.	If tidal system has eroded into other valuable habitat areas, such as seasonal ponds quicker than expected. Regional and significant sea level rise effects are observed more rapidly than anticipated.	Years 5 - 10	Assess whether observed changes are due to restoration actions or system-wide change.	Close off selected tidal channels or accept the reduced accommodation space (would require agency consultation).	Closing off a maximum of 1 tidal channel.

NOTES:

¹ All applicable permit conditions and avoidance and minimization measures identified in the permits would be applied to Adaptive Management Activities. If working within the permitted work windows is not feasible, then the District would notify and discuss with the agencies prior to conducting the activities to ensure that impacts are being minimized.

Conservation Measures

Please refer to the proposed Project biological assessment for standard best management practices, spill prevention plans, storm water pollution prevention plans, and other general conservation measures. The following conservation measures are with regard to SMHM and CCR.

1. Service-Approved Qualified Biologist(s) and Monitor(s). Permittee shall submit to the Service for written approval, the names and resumes of all qualified biologists and biological monitors involved in conducting surveys and/or monitoring work.

A qualified biologist is an individual who shall have a minimum of five years of academic training and professional experience in biological sciences and related resource management activities with a minimum of two years conducting surveys for each species that may be present within the project area.

A biological monitor is an individual who shall have academic and professional experience in biological sciences and related resource management activities as it pertains to this proposed Project, experience with construction-level biological monitoring, be able to recognize species that may be present within the project area, and be familiar with the habits and behavior of those species.

2. Special-Status Species and Sensitive Habitat Training. The qualified biologist shall develop a training program on special-status species biology, identification, and sensitive habitat avoidance for field management and construction personnel on the importance of protecting environmental resources. The qualified biologist(s) developing the training shall have experience in CCR breeding ecology, and vocalizations, and knowledge and experience in SMHM biology and habitat requirements. Communication efforts and training shall take place during preconstruction meetings so that construction personnel are aware of their responsibilities and the importance of compliance. Construction personnel shall be educated in the types of sensitive resources located in the Action Area and the measures required to avoid impacts on those resources. Materials covered in the training program shall include environmental rules and regulations of the specific project and requirements for limiting activities to the construction right-of-way and avoiding demarcated sensitive resource areas. Training seminars shall educate construction supervisors and managers on the need for resource avoidance and protection, roles and responsibilities, and Agreement measures. If new construction personnel are added to the project, the contractor shall ensure the new personnel receive the mandatory training prior to starting work.
3. Silt and turbidity curtains. Silt and turbidity curtains would also be installed within the excavated channels to intercept turbidity plumes generated from earthwork activities and thereby reduce any decrease in water quality.
4. Nighttime Work. Nighttime work shall be avoided to the extent feasible. If nighttime work cannot be avoided, lighting shall be directed to the work area, and away from

marsh habitat. Any nighttime security lighting outside of work hours shall be directed onto equipment, not marsh areas.

5. Extreme High Tides. Project-related activities, including construction, vegetation management (i.e., clearing and grubbing, removal of suitable SMHM habitat prior to ground disturbance, removal of invasive and non-native species, and planting of native species), and any maintenance activities approved within tidal or non-tidal marsh habitat (excluding upland habitat) shall be scheduled to avoid two hours on either side of extreme high tides. For this proposed Project, extreme high tides are in excess of 7.0 feet North American Vertical Datum of 1988 as predicted at the Port Chicago tide gauge.
6. Herbicides. Herbicides used for vegetation management activities in tidal marsh and non-tidal marsh habitat (excluding upland habitat) shall be Environmental Protection Agency-certified for use in or immediately adjacent to aquatic environments.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

7. Suitable SMHM Habitat. Suitable habitat for SMHM shall include tidal brackish marsh, including bulrush and cattails, and non-tidal pickleweed habitat, including diked seasonal wetlands with pickleweed.
8. Qualified SMHM Biologist. A qualified SMHM biologist approved by CDFW and the Service shall be present on site at all times that work activities are being conducted in suitable SMHM habitat. Minimum qualifications for the qualified SMHM biologist are a 4-year college degree in biology or related field, or a graduate degree in biology, and a minimum of 2 years of professional experience in conducting surveys and/or monitoring for SMHM. The qualified SMHM biologist shall document compliance with all SMHM-related avoidance and minimization measures. The qualified SMHM biologist shall have the authority to stop project activities if any of the measures are not being adhered to.

A SMHM monitor approved by CDFW and the Service shall have academic and professional experience in biological sciences and related resource management activities as it pertains to this project, experience with construction-level biological monitoring, and be able to recognize and be familiar with the habits and behavior of SMHM.

9. Observation of SMHM. If any SMHM individuals or nests are observed in the work area, all construction activities shall cease within a 50-foot radius of the detection. The individual(s) shall be allowed to leave the area before work is resumed. If the SMHM does not move on its own volition or a nest is observed, the qualified SMHM biologist shall contact CDFW and the Service for further guidance on how to proceed.
10. Preconstruction Surveys. A qualified SMHM biologist shall identify and mark suitable SMHM habitat within 14 days prior to the planned start of project activities. Within 48

hours of project construction, and prior to the initiation of work each day in suitable SMHM habitat, a qualified SMHM biologist shall conduct a preconstruction survey of all suitable habitat that may be directly or indirectly impacted by the day's activities. Rakes or similar hand-tools may be used to part vegetation and allow for more thorough inspection of dense vegetation.

11. Avoidance. Ground disturbance to suitable SMHM habitat shall be avoided to the extent feasible. All construction equipment and materials shall be staged on existing roadways or staging areas and away from suitable SMHM habitats when not in use.
12. Vegetation Removal. Where SMHM habitat cannot be avoided - such as for channel excavation, access routes and grading, or anywhere else that vegetation in suitable SMHM habitat could be trampled or crushed by work activities - vegetation shall be removed to ground level from the ground disturbance work area. Any vegetation removal necessary in suitable SMHM habitat or within 50 feet of suitable SMHM habitat shall be conducted according to the following:
 - i) Vegetation removal shall be conducted under the supervision of a qualified SMHM biologist.
 - ii) No more than three workers shall conduct vegetation removal while being monitored by a single qualified SMHM biologist or SMHM monitor. Additional workers shall be allowed to perform vegetation removal as long as they are accompanied by additional qualified SMHM biologists or SMHM monitors, accordingly.
 - iii) Workers clearing vegetation shall not be greater than 50 feet from a qualified SMHM biologist or SMHM monitor.
 - iv) Vegetation removal shall begin furthest from the largest contiguous suitable SMHM habitat and proceed towards it, providing cover for SMHM and allowing individuals to move passively toward the contiguous suitable SMHM habitat as vegetation is being removed.
 - v) Vegetation shall initially be disturbed, allowing SMHM to move from the area of disturbance toward the area of largest contiguous marsh. Vegetation may be trimmed using non-motorized hand-tools (e.g. grass whips, loppers, rakes, trowels, hoes, and/or shovels), or motorized hand-tools limited to a string-trimmer, if necessary, to a height sufficient to determine that no SMHM or their nests are present. Once the qualified SMHM biologist has determined that the vegetation is clear of SMHM and their nests, motorized hand-tools (e.g., walk-behind mower, string trimmers, etc.) may be utilized to remove the remaining vegetation to ground level. Vegetation removal in SMHM habitat shall only be conducted with a qualified SMHM biologist or SMHM monitor walking in front of the vegetation removal crew to confirm that SMHM are not in the vegetation removal path.

- vi) Removed vegetation shall not be stockpiled within the work area/exclusion zones or near roads or staging areas due to the risk of re-occupation by SMHM.
13. Temporary SMHM Exclusion Fencing. To protect SMHM from construction activities and traffic, exclusion fencing shall be installed following vegetation removal between the active work area and suitable SMHM habitat adjacent to the active work area. In the footprint of the new tidal channels to be constructed, a qualified SMHM biologist shall be on-site to monitor all work activities in lieu of exclusion fencing.
- The SMHM exclusion fencing shall be made of a material that does not allow SMHM to climb or pass through. The SMHM exclusion fencing shall be a minimum above-ground height of 30 inches and at least 12 inches higher than any adjacent vegetation, and the bottom shall be buried to a depth of at least 4 inches so SMHM cannot crawl under the fence. Any supports for the SMHM exclusion fencing (e.g., t-posts) shall be placed on the inside of the project area. The last 5 feet of the SMHM exclusion fencing shall be angled away from the road to direct wildlife away from the road. A qualified SMHM biologist shall be on site during SMHM exclusion fencing installation and shall check the fencing alignment and installation to ensure no SMHM are present. The SMHM exclusion fencing shall be inspected daily and repaired immediately.
14. Side Casting of Materials in Suitable SMHM Habitat. No materials shall be side cast (e.g. during tidal channel excavation) at any time into suitable SMHM habitat.
15. Notification. If a qualified biologist has requested work stoppage due to take of listed species, or if a dead or injured SMHM is observed, the Service will be notified within one day by email or telephone.

California Clapper Rail

16. Suitable Rail Habitat. Suitable rail habitat shall include fully tidal brackish marsh, tidal channels, or anywhere CCR have been observed.
17. Qualified Rail Biologist. A qualified rail biologist approved by CDFW and the Service shall be present on site at all times that work activities are being conducted in suitable rail habitat. Minimum qualifications for the qualified rail biologist are a 4-year college degree in biology or related field, or a graduate degree in biology, and a minimum of 2 years of professional experience in conducting surveys and/or monitoring for rails. The qualified biologist shall have knowledge of rail biology and vocalizations, and familiarity with both CCR and California black rail (*Laterallus jamaicensis coturniculus*) and their nests. The qualified rail biologist shall document compliance with all rail-related avoidance and minimization measures. The qualified rail biologist shall have the authority to stop project activities if any of the measures are not being adhered to.

A rail monitor approved by CDFW and the Service shall have academic and professional experience in biological sciences and related resource management activities as it pertains to this project, experience with construction-level biological

monitoring, be able to recognize and be familiar with the habits and behavior of rail species.

18. Preconstruction Surveys. A qualified rail biologist shall identify and mark suitable rail habitat within 14 days prior to the planned start of project activities. Within 48 hours of project construction, and prior to the initiation of work each day, a qualified rail biologist shall conduct a pre-construction survey of all areas within suitable rail habitat or within 50 feet of suitable rail habitat that may be directly or indirectly impacted by the day's activities.
19. Nonbreeding Season. During the non-breeding season (September 1 to January 31), construction activities requiring entry by workers into or within 50 feet of suitable rail habitat shall be conducted with a qualified rail biologist or rail monitor present. If rails are observed within or near the work area during the non-breeding season, a minimum 50-foot no-disturbance buffer from the observation location shall be established until the rail biologist or rail monitor confirms that the rails have left the area.
20. Breeding Season. Every attempt shall be made to avoid construction activities, or other work involving heavy equipment, within or immediately adjacent to suitable rail habitat during the breeding season from February 1 through August 31. Anywhere within 50 feet of suitable rail habitat and/or within 600 feet of a detection location, a qualified rail biologist or rail monitor shall be present for the duration of project activities, as described below. In addition:
 - i) If construction activities, or other work involving heavy equipment, within or immediately adjacent to suitable rail habitat cannot be avoided during the breeding season (February 1 through August 31), surveys shall be conducted to determine rail nesting locations. Survey methods for rails shall follow *Site-Specific Protocol for Monitoring Marsh Birds: Don Edwards San Francisco Bay and San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuges*, version 1.0 (Wood *et al* 2016), which was used for surveys in 2019 and 2020 and has been approved by the Service specifically for use on the proposed Project. Surveys must be done under onsite direction of a biologist holding a current 10(a)(1)(A) permit for such activities and survey results shall be provided to CDFW and the Service prior to initiation of project activities.
 - ii) No breeding rails: If no breeding rails are detected during protocol surveys, then project activities may proceed within or adjacent to suitable rail habitat. A qualified rail biologist or rail monitor shall remain on site for the duration of construction activities in, and within 50 feet of, suitable rail habitat.
 - iii) Work within 600 feet of breeding rails: If protocol surveys determine that breeding rails are present in or immediately adjacent to the project area, project activities may proceed outside of suitable rail habitat beyond a 600-foot radius from each estimated detection location. Every attempt shall be made to conduct no work within the 600-foot radius from each estimated detection location. For any work within suitable rail habitat and/or within 600 feet of detection locations, a qualified rail biologist shall be present for the duration of project activities.

- iv) Work within 300-600 feet of breeding rails: If protocol surveys determine that breeding rails are present in or immediately adjacent to the project area, limited construction activities may be conducted during the breeding season (February 1 – August 31) if necessary, between 300- and 600-feet of a detection location, with a qualified rail biologist present and implementation of the following:
 - (1) Activities may only occur if there is a substantial non-habitat barrier (e.g., open water of a major slough channel, berms, roads) in between the work area and the detection location or if a commercially available portable acoustic barrier panel is placed close to the noise source and between the work area and the detection location.
 - (2) Activities shall be limited to surveys (including installation of survey markers with hammers); removal of vegetation with non-motorized hand tools such as grass whips, loppers, rakes, etc.; targeted herbicide applications; native plant harvesting and planting; fencing installation; and earth moving with shovels, picks, and other hand tools. Additional activities may be approved after further discussion with CDFW and the Service, but may require re-initiation of section 7 consultation.
 - (3) Qualified rail biologists and rail monitors shall have maps or global positioning systems locations of the confirmed rail detection locations and shall proceed cautiously and minimize time spent in areas near where rails were detected.
- v) Work within 300 feet of breeding rails: During the rail breeding season, no work activities shall occur within 300 feet of a rail detection location, except along the western side of the North Reach where there is a substantial (100-foot) non-habitat barrier between work areas and breeding rail activities in Peyton Marsh (*i.e.*, the Transmontaigne pipeline, access roads, berms, ditches, and fences). Activities along this western side of the North Reach adjacent to the non-habitat barrier described above shall be limited to herbicide application and use of non-motorized hand-tools only. In other areas of the North Reach, no work activities may occur within 300 feet of rail detection locations during rail breeding season.
- vi) If an alarmed rail or rail nest is detected, work shall be stopped, and workers shall leave the immediate area carefully and quickly. An alternate route shall be selected that avoids this area by at least 300 feet for 40 days, and the location of the sighting shall be recorded to inform future activities in the area.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR §402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action”. For the proposed Project, the Action Area encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the proposed Project and the broader area that, while outside the construction zone, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, or

movement associated with the proposed Project. The Action Area of the proposed Project totals approximately 1,165 acres. This total reflects the entire 384-acre Project site, in addition to 759 acres of tidal marsh and 22 acres of non-tidal pickleweed marsh outside the Project area but subjected to noise levels above 3 dBA (A-weighted decibels) above background noise levels.

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. "Jeopardize the continued existence of" means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the SMHM: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*). Both subspecies are listed as endangered. The status of SMHM and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at:

https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf.

Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

California Clapper Rail

The status of CCR and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*

(Service 2013). This document can be found at:
https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf.
Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Environmental Baseline

The *Environmental baseline* refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequence to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the environmental baseline.

The Action Area is on the southern shore of the Suisun Bay region, adjacent to the Carquinez Strait. The proposed Project site is located in unincorporated Contra Costa County approximately 3 miles east of the City of Martinez, along the lower 2.5 miles of Walnut Creek and 1.5 miles of Pacheco Creek. The Walnut Creek watershed is the largest watershed in Contra Costa County, and one of the largest in the Bay Area, draining approximately 150 square miles. Land use within the project site is largely industrial, with areas of undeveloped land. The Action Area is composed of historic tidal marshland, Lower Walnut Creek, and Pacheco Creek and includes tidal and non-tidal areas, but historically was nearly entirely tidal. In the 1960s, the lowest four miles of Walnut and Pacheco Creeks became part of a Corps flood control project. The intertidal salt marsh (tidal marsh) throughout the Action Area provides suitable but marginal habitat for CCR and suitable habitat for SMHM, including areas of non-tidal wetlands and upland habitats suitable for SMHM scattered within and along the edges of the intertidal marsh.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Trapping efforts within the Action Area in the locality of Shell Marsh, Peyton Slough, and Pacheco Creek have indicated SMHM presence according to the California Natural Diversity Database. The species was also trapped in Point Edith Wildlife Area, adjacent to the Action Area, throughout the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s; as well as in Avon-Port Chicago Marsh in 1997 (CDFW 2018). In 2008, four SMHM were captured during trapping efforts in the north part of the South Reach in pickleweed-dominated vegetation (Monk & Associates, Inc. 2008). Salt marsh harvest mice are assumed to occupy suitable tidal and non-tidal pickleweed marsh habitats within the Action Area. The SMHM is likely to occur in the North, Middle, South, and Pacheco Reaches of the proposed Project.

California Clapper Rail

The CCR occurs sporadically and in low numbers at various locations throughout the Suisun Marsh area. They have been found recurrently since 1978 in shoreline marshes from Martinez

east to Port Chicago, Suisun and Hill Sloughs, and the western reaches of Cutoff Slough (Herzog *et al.* 2005; Service 2013).

Occurrences of CCR from 2006 and 2009 in Point Edith Wildlife Area were documented approximately 0.25 to 0.75 mile east of the proposed restoration activities (Estrella 2007; WRA 2009). There is a record of a 2008 detection in the marsh to the west of Interstate 680, approximately 1.5 miles from the restoration area (CDFW 2018). Surveys in 2014 along Waterfront Road at the south end of the North Reach of the Action Area did not locate any CCR (LSA 2014), nor did surveys in 2016 along the pipeline east of the bio-oxidation pond east of the North Reach (LSA 2016a) or those along Waterfront Road at the north end of the Middle Reach of the Action Area (LSA 2016b). California clapper rails were not documented by surveys conducted from 2011 to 2017 east of the Marathon (formerly Tesoro) Martinez Refinery at Pt. Edith Wildlife Area, nor adjacent to Walnut Creek at Waterfront Road (WRA 2017). There were no CCR observed in the Action Area in 2019 (ESA 2019).

Surveys in accordance with the *Site-Specific Protocol for Monitoring Marsh Birds: Don Edwards San Francisco Bay and San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuges*, version 1.0 (Wood *et al.* 2016) detected no CCR in the Action Area in 2020. However, 11-13 individual California black rails were detected within the Action Area, in Peyton Marsh and in the fringing marsh along Walnut Creek, adjacent the North Reach (Liu 2020).

Although habitat for the CCR does not occur within the work limits other than at the breaches themselves, habitat exists directly adjacent to the work limits and within the Action Area. Even though in these adjacent areas habitat conditions are considered suitable for CCR, they are not currently ideal due to their brackish nature. Typically, CCR occur in very low densities in tidal brackish marshes in Suisun Bay. Given their 2006 and 2009 occurrences nearby, it is possible CCR could occur in the Action Area during construction or associated long-term activities. Presence in the Action Area is more likely in the North Reach compared to the Middle, South and Pacheco Reaches where suitable habitat is even more limited.

Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

The proposed Project includes implementation of *Conservation Measures* as described above under *Description of the Proposed Action*. Even with these measures in place, adverse effects to SMHM and CCR are likely. Effects of the proposed Project can be categorized best as stemming from either habitat loss/conversion or disturbance from construction, maintenance and adaptive management of the restoration project and are discussed as such here.

Habitat Loss/Conversion

The proposed Project is likely to result in a significant increase in CCR habitat (93 acres) and slight overall increase in SMHM habitat (10.5 acres), while returning the tidal regime to a portion of its historic range. In addition, the Project includes 32 acres of transitional lowland grassland restoration, which will serve as vital areas to transition to wetlands, over a potential five-foot rise in sea level. The Project's proximity to significant existing tidal marsh acreage suggests that, with successful restoration, the Project should greatly enhance connectivity for marsh-dependent species in the region.

Construction of the proposed Project will remove a substantial amount of non-tidal marsh habitat so that it may be converted to tidal marsh and tidal channel habitat. In these areas, vegetation will either be systematically removed for the excavation of new tidal channels, flooded when tidal flows return to the site or destroyed and/or fragmented in areas, due to levee breaching, levee creation, and other activities that involve movement of soil.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mice

Each of the aforementioned possible effects to non-tidal pickleweed habitat results in its being temporarily unsuitable for use by SMHM. This condition may result in short-term, localized declines in SMHM numbers due to movement of SMHM to adjacent habitat. Existing non-tidal pickleweed marsh that is located outside of the grading area and above tidal influence will be kept in place. It is anticipated that SMHM habitat that is unaffected by project activities or lies on nearby lands may continue to support SMHM until and after the establishment of fully functioning tidal wetlands, at which point they may even be a source for SMHM repatriation of the Project site.

Specifically, the proposed Project involves the removal of 82.2 discontinuous acres of non-tidal pickleweed marsh habitat for SMHM. As flooded marshes accrete soil and vegetation becomes successfully established, this loss will be replaced with 93 acres of fully tidal marsh habitat, also suitable for SMHM. This conversion would result in an increase in suitable SMHM habitat of 10.5 acres. In addition, the proposed Project will restore 32 acres of lowland grassland, creating high tide refugia and SMHM foraging habitat in the short term. This element was also designed to provide transition space for migration of marsh, accommodating five feet of sea level rise in the long-term.

Levee lowering will involve a phased removal of earth to provide continuous flood protection and to limit the risk of uncontrolled breaching, which could otherwise injure or kill SMHM. However, habitat conversion may result in the disturbance, harm, injury, or death of SMHM through the loss and degradation of their habitat from flooding. Displaced SMHM may also be more visible to predators as they disperse to find available habitat elsewhere and may have to compete for resources in occupied habitat. Disturbance to females may cause abandonment or failure of the current litter. Thus, displaced SMHM may suffer from increased predation, competition, mortality, and reduced reproductive success.

California Clapper Rail

Because the majority of vegetation to be removed is non-tidal wetland, which is unsuitable for rails, the proposed Project is not likely to cause negative effects to CCR in terms of habitat conversion. However, 2.58 acres of CCR tidal brackish marsh habitat will be permanently lost through grading associated with project construction, primarily involving tidal breaches. The loss of those few acres however, is well offset by the net increase of 93 acres of tidal marsh habitat, which could better support rails into the future should they continue to occasionally visit the Project site. Though more habitat will be present in physical structure, due to brackish water conditions, it is expected that rails will only ever inhabit the site in low densities.

Construction, Maintenance and Ongoing Adaptive Management

Construction, maintenance and ongoing adaptive management associated with the proposed Project will result in equipment noise, vibration, visual disturbance, and crushing risk. These effects may interfere with normal wildlife behaviors such as feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors of both SMHM and CCR.

The District's plan to remove vegetation in SMHM habitat in a phased approach beginning with hand tools will allow SMHM the opportunity to flee the area, reducing the risk of potential injury and/or mortality from use of construction equipment. Additionally, removing vegetation starting with the furthest area away from the largest contiguous SMHM habitat and working toward it should reduce the possibility of SMHM running toward hazardous areas. However, as mice are not predictable in their escape movements, it is possible that one or two may be wounded or killed in fleeing the area. Construction fencing, designed to isolate work areas and reduce risk of crushing mortality throughout most of the Project site, could potentially entrap SMHM in the areas proposed for channel excavation since not all vegetation will be removed from the fenced area. However, since the proposed fenced areas are relatively large, SMHM may have sufficient space to seek refuge while excavation is ongoing and a qualified SMHM biologist will walk directly in front of heavy equipment to watch for SMHM and prevent their injury. Natural food sources may be reduced as a result of temporary habitat disturbance and loss; however, areas surrounding the suitable habitat could provide the refugia and shelter needed by the SMHM temporarily during the duration of construction.

Foremost among the non-habitat related effects to SMHM and CCR from construction and maintenance of the proposed Project is noise. The District proposes to utilize graders, water trucks and other large equipment to conduct earth-moving activities related to initial construction, ongoing maintenance and adaptive management. Specifically, significant noise may result from construction activities such as grading, excavation of channels, levee breaches and levee creation.

In the absence of site-specific noise measurements or equipment-specific Project specifications, the Service uses general guidance regarding construction sound levels for various types of equipment measured in past projects across a range of locations. When multiple pieces of equipment are operating concurrently, the decibel levels may be additive; two noises of equal level (+/- 1 dBA) combine to raise the noise level by 3 dBA. However, if two noises differ by more than 10 dBA,

there is no combined increase in the noise level; the higher output covers any other noise (Washington Department of Transportation [WSDOT] 2015). For the proposed Project, a maximum noise level from equipment is expected to be approximately 90 dBA at 50 feet and occur intermittently for several months when the grading and excavation activities occur in each reach.

To estimate the noise attenuation effect of distance, decibel levels can be estimated to typically reduce by 6.0-7.5 dBA/doubling of distance for “point” source noise, such as construction noise (WSDOT 2015; California Department of Transportation [Caltrans] 2016). For the proposed Project, a mid-level reduction of 6.75 dBA/doubling of distance was estimated.

Some level of ambient noise is present onsite regardless of construction noise. South of the North reach and east of the Middle and South reaches, varying degrees of industrial activity are ongoing. Figure 1 illustrates approximate ambient background noise levels likely present on and surrounding the project site, as well as the distance out from the project site to which project-related sound would extend at a level at least 3 dBA above the approximate ambient noise level. According to Barber *et al.* (2009), noise levels above 3 dBA above background levels can result in a 50 percent reduced listening area and 30 percent reduced alerting distance in wildlife while noise levels above 10 dBA above background levels can result in 90 percent reduced alerting distance. In a study by Rasmussen *et al.* (2009), lab mice exposed to construction noise levels 70-90 dBA above background levels for ≥ 1 hour/day during gestation led to decreased reproductive efficiency (by decreasing live birth rates and increasing the number of stillborn pups). The Transportation Noise Control Center (1997) found that noise levels over 80 dBA above background levels caused behavior disruption in foraging, breeding, egg incubation, and rearing of young in various bird species.

Figure 1. Approximate background noise levels and approximate extent to which proposed construction noise will reach into nearby habitat surrounding the proposed Project site.

Using a maximum equipment construction noise level of 90 dBA at 50 feet and a 6.75 dBA reduction/doubling of distance:

North Reach:

- 1,500-10,000 feet is required, depending on specific location of construction within the reach, for a project-related noise level of 90 dBA to attenuate below a level disruptive to normal wildlife behavior (≥ 3 dBA above background noise; Barber *et. al.* 2009).

Middle and South Reaches:

- 700-2,500 feet is required, depending on specific location of construction within the reach, for a project-related noise level of 90 dBA to attenuate below a level disruptive to normal wildlife behavior (≥ 3 dBA above background noise; Barber *et. al.* 2009).

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Figure 2 illustrates estimated total acreage of tidal marsh and non-tidal marsh habitat within which construction noise will be at least 3 dBA above background noise levels. Salt marsh harvest mice will be subjected to noise levels at or above 3 dBA above background, which may cause alterations to typical behavior, within:

- 747 acres of suitable habitat (699 acres of tidal marsh and 48 acres of non-tidal marsh) in and adjacent to the North Reach and
- 117 acres of suitable habitat (60 acres of tidal marsh and 57 acres of non-tidal marsh) in and adjacent to the Middle and South Reaches.

Figure 2. Approximate area of tidal (red) and non-tidal pickleweed habitat (pink) present within the proposed Project Action Area (area within which construction noise is at least 3 dBA above background noise levels).

Activities such as levee building, lowering, or breaching, and channel excavation could cause disturbance to SMHM within these areas. Intolerable levels of disturbance, including that from noise and visual effects, that force individual SMHM to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. In addition, SMHM fleeing the construction site may move into areas where they could be crushed by equipment. Finally, displaced individuals could also be exposed to increased competition and reduced reproductive success through abandonment of a nesting area, failure to breed, or abandonment or failure of a litter.

Monitoring, maintenance and ongoing adaptive management on the Project site could result in the same habitat and noise-related effects to SMHM as could occur during initial construction, as discussed above. Effects to SMHM could be increased if intense modification of new tidal

channels is necessary given ongoing maintenance and adaptive management, as detailed in columns entitled “Maximum Limits” in Tables 2 and 3 above. This would especially be the case if additional vegetation in suitable habitat was removed. However, when possible, all maintenance activities will be conducted outside of SMHM habitat and appropriate buffer areas, seasonal restrictions and all other conservation measures implemented during construction and listed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* above will also be implemented during long-term maintenance and management.

It is extremely challenging to anticipate how many SMHM could be harmed, injured or killed due to construction activities in conditions such as those that exist on the Project site and in the absence of baseline population data. Based on the *Conservation Measures* geared toward protection of SMHM, we anticipate SMHM will primarily be protected from, or have an opportunity to move away from, noise, vibration, visual disturbance and crushing risk. However, even with a biological monitor present, it is possible that a couple SMHM in each construction location and even a nest within the Project site could be missed by the monitor and thereby these individuals could be injured or killed. Additionally, it is reasonable to expect that an occasional SMHM might be missed by the monitor during the less intense disturbance involved with long term monitoring, maintenance, and adaptive management and thereby be injured or killed.

Overall, the proposed Project could result in local and temporary declines of SMHM due to habitat conversion and to noise, vibrations, visual disturbance and crushing risk associated with construction, maintenance or ongoing management activities within or adjacent to tidal marsh habitat. However, successful restoration of the project site should result in a net increase in 10.5 acres of suitable habitat for the species, which will likely have significant future benefits for the SMHM.

California Clapper Rail

As mentioned above, other than at the outer edges of the Project area where breaches will occur, CCR habitat does not exist on the Project site itself; however, it does exist directly adjacent in Peyton Marsh, Point Edith Marsh, and the fringing marsh along Walnut Creek. Figure 2 (above) illustrates estimated total acreage of adjacent tidal marsh within which construction noise will be at least 3 dBA above background noise levels. Exclusion buffers and portable sound barriers, where installed, will reduce the most direct visual and noise effects to CCR. However, CCR will still be subjected to noise levels at or above 3 dBA above background, which may cause alterations to typical behavior within:

- 699 acres of tidal marsh adjacent to the North Reach and
- 60 acres of tidal marsh adjacent to the Middle and South Reaches.

Equipment noise, vibration, and increased human activity associated with project construction, routine maintenance, or monitoring may cause disturbance to CCR in adjacent marshes, by interfering with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, breeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors of CCR. The CCR in Peyton Marsh, Point Edith Marsh, or the fringing marsh along Walnut Creek may be exposed to

predation if they are flushed from cover or prevented from seeking available cover. As CCR disperse to higher ground, they may experience increased predation exposure from active movement or by seeking shelter in vegetation communities with less dense canopy cover. As a result, displaced CCR may also be subject to increased competition for resources in more densely occupied habitat. Although the proposed timeline for work in and near suitable habitat aims to avoid this season, disturbance to females, if present, during the breeding season (February 1-August 31) may cause nest abandonment and the loss of all eggs and chicks in the nest. CCR could experience reduced ability to vocalize with conspecifics, difficulty in maintaining or establishing territories, or experience reduced hours for sleeping and foraging. All of these behaviors can result in increased stress levels.

To minimize adverse effects to breeding, work in suitable habitat will occur outside of the breeding season if possible, with additional minimization measures (described above under *Conservation Measures*) implemented under circumstances when it cannot. Suitable habitat only occurs along the outer edges of the Action Area. Any CCR here that are disturbed by adjacent construction could flee the site in the opposite direction toward areas of significant refuge in undisturbed suitable habitat at Peyton Marsh, Point Edith Marsh or the fringing marsh along Walnut Creek.

While the project description submitted during consultation included the potential use of sound barriers (during project activities occurring during CCR breeding season within 300-600 feet of a calling center), detailed equipment specifications and/or analysis of the specific noise attenuation effects were not provided to the Service. Therefore, the Service did not further evaluate the degree to which construction noise may or may not be attenuated or reflected away from adjacent occupied listed species habitat.

Maintenance and management actions that could occur in or around rail habitat would include activities such as excavation of sediment or debris from tidal channels, regrading breaches or channels, replanting of native plants, non-native invasive species control, closing of channels, and levee maintenance. These activities could result in the same habitat and noise-related effects to CCR as could occur during initial construction, as discussed above. Effects to CCR could be increased if intense modification of new tidal channels is necessary given ongoing maintenance and adaptive management, as detailed in columns entitled "Maximum Limits" in Tables 2 and 3 above. This would especially be the case if additional breaches in tidal habitat are necessary or if newly established tidal channels are closed off. However, when possible, all maintenance activities will be conducted outside of CCR habitat, and appropriate buffer areas, seasonal restrictions and all other conservation measures implemented during construction and listed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* above will also be implemented during long-term maintenance and management.

Vegetation management associated with the project, including herbicide application and mechanical removal, as well as outplanting of native plants, could occur in breeding or non-breeding season for CCR and would result in some visual disturbance to CCR. Visual disturbance will be minimized with implementation of the *Conservation Measures*. No substantial noise or vibrations should occur, however, as crews will access the site on foot and use only non-motorized tools. Herbicide will be applied in accordance with the label and other

protection measures. Likewise, monitoring will be conducted with crews accessing the marsh on foot and acting in accordance with the *Conservation Measures* noted above and in the MAMP.

Though habitat conditions are considered suitable for CCR, they are not currently ideal due to their brackish nature. Typically, CCR occur in very low densities in tidal brackish marshes in Suisun Bay. Overall, based on the low densities observed in the recent past and lack of detections during 2020 surveys and the relatively low quality brackish conditions present in the project area, under the worst scenario, the proposed Project should adversely affect relatively low numbers of CCR. Restoration of tidal flows to the Project site will increase physical habitat space for CCR by a net 93 acres, which will likely have future benefit for CCR.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed Project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed Project. Sea level rise is ongoing and reasonably certain to occur in the future in the Action Area as greenhouse gas emissions continue to contribute to climate change.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of SMHM and CCR, the environmental baseline for the Action Area, the effects of the proposed Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Lower Walnut Creek Restoration Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of SMHM and CCR. The Service reached this conclusion because the Project-related effects to these species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of appreciably reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of these species based on the following:

1. The proposed action gives full consideration to, and is consistent with, the survival and recovery needs of the SMHM and CCR and the role of the Action Area in providing for those needs;
2. Given the implementation of the *Conservation Measures* described in this biological opinion, adverse impacts are likely to be small in magnitude, temporary, short-term and geographically local;
3. Adverse effects to CCR individuals are likely to be low and though higher for SMHM, will be temporary (given likely repatriation for SMHM), and are not likely to have long-term adverse population-level impacts; and
4. If successful, the proposed Project will increase habitat quantity and quality for both SMHM and CCR.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by the Service as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the Service to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary; and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

Conservation Measures proposed by the project proponent and described above in the *Description of the Proposed Action* will reduce, but do not eliminate, the likelihood of incidental take of these species during the proposed Project.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There is a risk of harm, injury and mortality as a result of the proposed construction, monitoring, maintenance, and adaptive management activities and the associated permanent and temporary loss/degradation of suitable habitat over the 10-year period. However, the Service anticipates that incidental take of SMHM will be difficult to detect because of the variable, unknown size of the resident population over time and the difficulty in finding killed or injured small mammals. Incidental take of SMHM is anticipated in the form of:

- Injury or mortality to all SMHM within one nest, plus 5 adult SMHM during construction (maximum one full year) and one adult SMHM every three years thereafter during maintenance and adaptive management, for the ten-year life of the project. These injuries

or mortalities are primarily anticipated to occur due to crushing by equipment, despite a monitor being present, within the initial 27 acres of proposed vegetation removal and grading, as well as that which occurs during future maintenance and management. It may also occur during use of the access roads and staging areas during construction, maintenance, or management.

- Harm of all SMHM within the 864 noise-affected acres, by impairing essential behaviors such as foraging, breeding, nesting, rearing of young, and predator evasion due to construction noise, vibrations and visual effects.

California Clapper Rail

The Service anticipates incidental take of CCR will be difficult to detect or quantify because the elusive nature of this species, their small size, and cryptic coloration make the finding of a dead specimen unlikely. Due to construction and implementation of maintenance, adaptive management and monitoring activities over a 10-year period, incidental take of CCR is anticipated in the form of:

- Harm of all CCR within the 759 noise-affected acres, by impairing essential behaviors such as foraging, breeding, nesting, rearing of young, and predator evasion due to construction noise, vibrations and visual effects.

Upon implementation of the reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of SMHM and CCR associated with the Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this biological opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the levels of anticipated take are not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the SMHM and CCR.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed Project to the SMHM and CCR:

1. The Corps through the applicant and its contractors will minimize the potential for harm, injury and mortality of SMHM and harm of CCR.

Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps must ensure compliance with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. The proposed action will be implemented as described in this biological opinion, the Biological Assessment, the Monitoring and Adaptive Management Plan and other associated Project materials, including the proposed *Conservation Measures*.
2. The final Monitoring and Adaptive Management Plan (which includes as an appendix the Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Monitoring Plan), having been reviewed in draft by the Service but not having been completed by the District before the issuance of this biological opinion, shall not significantly differ from the reviewed draft and shall be provided to the Service upon completion.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the proposed Project is approached or exceeded, the Corps through the applicant shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR §402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or Service-approved biologist. Notification will be made to Jana Affonso, the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the applicant through the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/BIOS>).

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are Jana Affonso, the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the

purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following action:

1. The Service recommends that post-construction monitoring for federally-listed species is conducted for restoration projects in the Bay Area, in order to determine the extent to which restoration is improving habitat onsite for these species. For consistency with recent surveys at the Project site, CCR monitoring should be done by a biologist holding a current 10(a)(1)(A) permit and in accordance with the *Site-Specific Protocol for Monitoring Marsh Birds: Don Edwards San Francisco Bay and San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuges*, version 1.0 (Wood *et al* 2016).

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION- CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Lower Walnut Creek Restoration Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16.

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

(1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and

(2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Valary Bloom, Endangered Species Biologist, at Valary_Bloom@fws.gov or (916) 930-2645 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Coordinator, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 08FBDT00-2020-F-0038 in any future correspondence regarding this Project.

Sincerely,

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

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